

ISOLATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF AMYLASE-PRODUCING BACTERIA FROM DIFFERENT SOIL SAMPLES OF DISTRICT ABBOTTABAD

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Abstract

Amylases are crucial hydrolase enzymes that can hydrolyze starch molecules and produce a variety of end-products like dextrin and small polymers made of glucose units. The current study addresses the lack of comprehensive knowledge about the diversity and potential of amylase-producing bacteria in different soil samples of Abbottabad district, Pakistan. The research seeks to isolate and characterize amylase-producing bacterial strains from six different locations, namely the Salhad damping site, Salhad fields, Havelian fruit mandi damping site, garden soil of Ayub Medical complex, Nathiagali, and Poultry farm Kakul village Abbottabad. Through this investigation, the study aims to identify promising amylase-producing bacterial isolates that can be utilized for potential biotechnological applications. The media used in the experiment included Luria-Bertani (LB) agar and broth, as well as starch agar media. The isolation of bacteria from the soil samples was done through serial dilution. Diluted samples were plated on LB agar and incubated, leading to the appearance of distinct colonies after 24 hours. Pure cultures were obtained from these colonies after additional incubation. The bacterial isolates were symmetrically labeled and then subjected to morphological identification using Gram staining and motility tests. Colony morphology was also observed by streaking bacteria on nutrient and LB media. Biochemical testing was performed, including the coagulase test, catalase test, oxidase test, indole test, and methyl-red test. For primary screening of amylase-producing bacteria, starch hydrolysis tests were conducted on starch agar media. Isolates showing significant zones of hydrolysis tests were selected for secondary screening. The potential isolates were assessed for their ability to produce amylase through submerged fermentation in a production medium. The crude enzyme was separated from the culture media and its activity was checked using starch agar plates. The study provides valuable insight into the diversity and potential of amylase-producing bacteria in Abbottabad district soil samples. The findings may have implications for further biotechnological applications, of enzyme production from these bacterial isolates and hold promise for cost-effective

INTRODUCTION

Enzymes are chemical substances that are produced by living cells. Enzymes are biological catalysts that speed up chemical reactions without being utilized in the reaction (Oyeleke & Oduwole, 2009). Enzymes process all the synthetic and degradative processes that occurs in living organisms. Depending on varying characteristics, enzymes are classified into multiple groups. Based on substrate, enzymes are classified as Amylase, cellulase, lipase, and pectinase. Among these, Amylases encompass a group of enzymes that break the α -1,4 glycosidic linkage present in starch, leading to the formation of dextrin and various other monomers of glucose (Souza, 2010).

Amylases are studied worldwide due to their vital physiological and biotechnological applications. Amylases are the most crucial enzymes and can be obtained from a wide range of sources like plants, animals, and microbes (Kalyani & Rajesh, 2018). But the amylases that are produced by microbes hold significant importance due to their features like bulk production, easy manipulation, and less time consumption. In addition to this, Amylases derived from bacteria are known because they are highly stable and enhance productivity, and these enzymes have low production costs (Ravindar & Elangovan, 2013). Studies have shown that amylase-producing bacteria can be isolated from soil and the environment.

Soil is a habitat that is vigorous for all diversity of life and provides shelter to many animals including invertebrates such as worms and insects, mammals including rabbits, rodents, and badgers. The soil is an ideal habitat for a complex group of microorganisms such as bacteria, algae, fungi, and protozoa (Bhattarai, Bhattarai, & Pandey, 2015). Microorganisms play a very important role in the production of enzymes. The selection of the right organisms is very important to obtain a high yield of the desired enzyme for industrial use. In each group of complex microorganisms' bacteria, algae, fungi, and actinomycetes, specific characteristics define them and their role in soil. The most abundant microbes in the soil are bacteria and Archaea (Berg, Tymoczko, & Stryer, 2007).

Amylases are endo hydro nucleases that not only act on α -1,4 glycosidic linkage of starch but also act on related oligosaccharides and polysaccharides and cleave it, because of which malt oligosaccharides and other glucose molecules release in α -anomeric form. So α -amylase is very important for animals that use starch as a primary source (Mohamed, Khan, Al-Bar, & ElShishtawy, 2014). Hydrolysis of starch by amylase is carried out in three steps: gelatinization, liquefaction, and saccharification (Kaneko, Ohno, Ohisa, & biochemistry, 2005). All these three processes consume a high amount of energy (Sun, Ge, Wang, Zhao, & Peng, 2009).

Amylase enzymes can be isolated from numerous sources like plants, animals, plants, and microorganisms. Although it can be isolated from plants and animals amylase that is isolated from microorganisms is more thermostable and have a higher yield (Pandey, Nigam, Soccol, Soccol, Singh, Mohan, et al., 2000). Moreover, the advantage of amylase enzymes produced from microbes have a capacity for economical bulk production, and the most important fact is to isolate the enzymes of the desired character, microbes can be easily manipulated (Lonsane & Ramesh, 1990). Amylase can be isolated from several fungal strains and can produce both extracellular and intracellular amylase depending upon the type of fermentation being used in production, (Chadha, Rubinder, & Saini, 2005; Ellaiah, Adinarayana, Sunitha, & Devi, 2003) but bacteria is considered best and preferred source in amylase producing microbes because it has not only high yield of the enzyme but produce enzyme extracellularly in a short period, which make it isolation easy (Abbas, 2009; Samanta, Mitra, Roy, Sinha, & Pal, 2013). Consequently, amylase produced by bacteria is the best alternative to a chemical that is used in starch hydrolysis (Shaw, Lin, Chen, & Chen, 1995). Microbes from that common amylase enzyme obtain include; *Aspergillus*, *Escherichia coli*, *pseudomonas sp.*, *Streptomyces sp.*, *Bacillus sp.*, *Lactobacillus sp.* (Sundarram, Murthy, & Microbiology, 2014).

Amylases are enzymes that are widely used in industries. In 1959 Dr. Jhokichi took amino acids

and began production of digestive enzymes by using dextrose in powder as well as in crystal form, from starch utilizing amylase and glucoamylase from then enzyme production began on an industrial level (Boyer & Ingle, 1972). So amylase is the enzyme that was first produced on an industrial level from a fungal source (Pandey, Nigam, Soccol, Soccol, Singh, Mohan, et al., 2000). Amylases have great industrial importance among all extracellular hydrolytic enzymes and occupy a particular position on an industrial scale. In the global enzyme market, the account of amylase enzyme is approximately 30% (Rao, Tanksale, Ghatge, Deshpande, & reviews, 1998; Sindhu, Singh, & Prased, 1997). As amylase's function is to hydrolyze the glycosidic linkage of starch and convert it into monosaccharide, disaccharide, trisaccharides, and oligomers. So α -amylase is very important for animals that use starch as a primary source (Mohamed et al., 2014). So, it is called a digestive enzyme (Pandey, Nigam, Soccol, Soccol, Singh, Mohan, et al., 2000). Amylases also possess various commercial applications mainly in biotechnological industries, especially the derivatives of α -amylase used in pharmaceutical, paper, textile, detergents, papers, baking, brewing, and sugar industries (Ashwini, Gaurav, Karthik, & Bhaskara Rao, 2011; Vijayalakshmi, Abha, Chander, & bioinformatics, 2012). In the biofuel industry amylase is used to convert starch into fermentable sugar (Atinuke & Samuel, 2015; M. Mobini-Dehkordi & F. A. J. J. B. T. W. Javan, 2012). Moreover, amylase enzymes play a major role in the biochemical cycle of carbon. Many researchers investigated the production of amylase enzyme by using multiple substrates and several microorganisms like bacteria, fungi, and yeast in a wide range of amylase enzyme applications (Bala et al., 2013).

In industry, amylases are of prime importance, thus increasing their demand. To meet the demand, researchers are struggling for the best sources of enzymes, especially amylases. This study, which involved the isolation, screening, and characterization of the amylase-producing bacteria, is also part of a similar struggle and was conducted in the district of Abbottabad, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

1.1 Aims:

This study focuses on the isolation, screening, and morphological and biochemical characterization of amylase-producing bacteria from the different soil samples of district Abbottabad.

1.2 Objectives:

The main objectives of the study are:

- To isolate the bacteria from the soil.
- To screen the best amylase-producing bacteria.
- To identify the best amylase-producing bacteria via morphological and biochemical tests.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Enzyme

Enzymes are the biological catalyst. It is highly effective in nature e that it initiate and speed up thousand the chemical reaction that takes place inside living organisms (Tiwari et al., 2015). It carries out all the degradative and synthetic processes. As enzymes are the biological catalyst that alter the way we prepared our food and increase the nutritional value of different food products so it is called " green" (Al-Maqtari, Waleed, & Mahdi, 2019). Enzymes are complex molecules and proteins in nature. The living cell produces an enzyme to increase the rate of an enormous and diverse range of chemical reactions. In all the essential activities of life, enzymes are involved such as DNA replication, transcription, protein synthesis, metabolism, cell control signals transduction frequently uses kinases and phosphatases (Chaudhary, Sagar, Kumar, Sengar, & Tomar, 2015).

2.2. Amylase

In the category of hydrolase enzyme, the majority of hydrolase enzymes that hydrolyze the glycosidic bond are amylases that breaks the glycosidic bond present in starch and produce dextrin and oligosaccharide (Farooq et al., 2021). Amylase is a part of the glycoside hydrolase family 13 (GH-13). The 1,4-glycosidic linkage in starch is hydrolyzed by amylase so-called glycoside hydrolases (Farooq et al., 2021). Amylases are classified into two categories i.e.; exo-amylase and endo-amylase. Exo-amylases undergo the hydrolysis of the non-reducing end of starch while endo-amylase undergoes the hydrolysis of glucosidic linkage that are present in the starch molecule

(Kamon et al., 2015). Presently amylase has great importance in the field of biotechnology (Gopinath et al., 2017). Amylase has a wide range of applications in biotechnology industries from food fermentation and textile to the paper industry. A

huge number of microbial enzymes are available in industries due to which chemical hydrolysis replaced by amylase hydrolysis in industrial processing (Pandey, Nigam, Soccol, Soccol, Singh, & Mohan, 2000).

Figure 1: Starch breaks down into glucose by Amylase.

2.3.1.1. Structure of α -amylase:

The source of α -amylase (α -1,4-glucan-4-glucanohydrolase) can be microorganisms, plants, and higher organisms (Kandra, 2003). The α -amylase is a member of the endo-nuclease family that breaks the α -D-(1,4) glycosidic bonds and catalyzes the first hydrolysis of starch into short oligosaccharide (Brayer, Luo, & Withers, 1995; Iulek et al., 2000; Kandra, 2003; Tangphatsornruang, Naconsie, Thammarongtham, & Narangajavana, 2005). α -Amylase neither breaks terminal glucose linkage nor α -1,6 linkages (Whitcomb & Lowe, 2007). Branched oligosaccharide 6-8 glucose units that contain both α -1,4 and 1,6 linkages and maltose, maltotriose, and oligosaccharide of varied length with an α -configuration and limit dextrins are the final product

produced by the action of α -amylase (Whitcomb & Lowe, 2007). The α -amylase and another amylolytic enzyme also play an important role in the breakdown of starch but α -amylase plays a key role in initiating the process (Tangphatsornruang et al., 2005). The amylase shows a three-dimensional structure that allows the amylase to bind its target site called a substrate, the cleavage of glycosidic linkage is done by the action of immense specialized catalytic groups (Iulek et al., 2000). The α -amylase of humans is a classically calcium-bearing enzyme. It is composed of an oligosaccharide chain that contains 512 amino acids and the molecular weight is 57.6 kDa (Whitcomb & Lowe, 2007). The protein consists of 3 domains; i.e, A, B, and C. Among all these three domains, the largest domain is domain A which is a

barrel in shape and 8 superstructures. The C domain appears independent domain with an unknown function and has a sheet structure connected with domain A through a simple polypeptide chain. Between these two domains, domain A and B, domain B is inserted and joined to domain A through a disulfide bond. Between the carboxyl end

of the domain A and B is a long cleft, where the active site (substrate-binding site) of α -amylase is located. Between domain A and B calcium (Ca^{2+}) is located that act as an allosteric activator as well as stabilizes the three-dimensional structure (Muralikrishna & Nirmala, 2005).

Figure 2: Structure of α -Amylase

2.3.2 β -Amylase:

The number for β -amylase from enzyme commission is EC 3.2.1.2. The non-reducing α -1,4-glycosidic linkages are hydrolyzed by β -amylase. It cannot hydrolyze the branches that are present in amylopectin or glycogen due to which hydrolysis remains incomplete. The ideal pH on which β -amylase shows maximum activity is 4.0-5.5. Fruits, seeds of higher plants, and sweet potatoes are the primary sources of β -amylase. (Das & Kayastha, 2019). When fruit becomes ripe, it has a sweet taste,

this sweetness of ripened fruit is because of starch breakdown into maltose by β -amylase. On an industrial scale as well as in research β -amylase have various uses. To understand the structure of starch and glycogen molecules by different methods as well as used in the brewing and distilling industry for fermentation. Also use for the production of high maltose syrup (S. Sivaramakrishnan, D. Gangadharan, K. M. Nampoothiri, C. R. Soccol, & A. Pandey, 2006).

Figure 3: Structure of β -amylase

2.3.3. γ -Amylase:

γ -Amylase has enzyme commission number EC 3.2.1.3. The basic function of γ -amylase unlike other enzymes, is to cleave the α -1,6 glycosidic linkage and produces glucose by hydrolyzing the amylose and

amyopectin non-reducing α -1,4-glycosidic bonds. It required an acidic environment for its proper functioning. So, the pH for γ -amylase is 3 (Argyros, Barrett, Caiazza, & Hogsett, 2017).

Figure 4: Structure of γ -Amylase

2.4. Starch:

The main substrate for α -amylase is starch. Starch is a major component of the Human diet. The starch that is chemically and enzymatically processed is used for the production of different products including, fructose and glucose syrup and derivatives of cyclodextrin and maltodextrin, starch hydrolysate (El-Fallal, Dohara, El-Sayed, & Omar, 2012). Additionally, sugar that is produced is fermented to produce ethanol. Starch is produced by a huge number of plants, but the starch produced by a few of them has gained industrial importance. Maize,

potato, wheat, and tapioca are the main source of starch but they have thermal resistance, thermal degradation, low shear resistance, and a high tendency toward retrogradation that limits their use in few industrial food applications (Agrawal, Pradeep, Chandraraj, & Gummadi, 2005; Gupta et al., 2003a; Van Der Maarel, Van der Veen, Uitdehaag, Leemhuis, & Dijkhuizen, 2002). Starch is very useful in different food products, due to which it gains more attention on an industrial scale as compared to other carbohydrate polymers. Starch plays an important role in the textural properties of many

foods and is widely used as a colloidal stabilizer, water retention agent, gelling agent, and a thickener and bulking agent in industrial applications (J. Singh, Kaur, & McCarthy, 2007). Starch is defined as a glucose polymer that joins to one another through glycosidic linkage. Two different forms of polymer Amylopectin and amylose are found in starch. Amylose is a linear chain polymer that is made up of 6000 glucose subunits that are linked by α -1,4-glycosidic linkages. Starch consists of 20-25%

amylose. While 70-80% of starch is Amylopectin which is a branched polymer. It consists of 10-60 and 15-45 glucose subunits that link together and form straight and branched chains, glucose subunits linked to one another by α -1,4 and α -1,6 glycosidic linkages. The glycosidic linkage α -1,4 is only that is hydrolyzing α -amylase (Goesaert, Slade, Levine, & Delcour, 2009; Sørensen et al., 2004).

Figure 5: Chemical structure of Amylose and Amylopectin

2.5 Advantages and Uses of Microbial Amylase:

The main benefit of microbes is to easily manipulate the enzymes with their necessary properties and their affordable bulk production capability. In the production of desired enzymes, it is simple to engineer bacteria. Enzymes produced from bacterial and fungal sources have predominated in commercial uses, although amylase has been derived from a variety of fungi, yeasts, bacteria, and actinomycetes (Manonmani, Kunhi, & Biotechnology, 1999). Amylases have been found in all the kingdoms of animals, plants, and microorganisms. During the past few decades, significant research has been done on extracellular α -amylase produced by several microbes (Lonsane & Ramesh, 1990). The enzymes are produced by a variety of *Bacillus* sp. and thermostable actinomycetes, such as *Thermomonospora* and *Thermoactinomyces* (Ben Massoud, Ben Ali, Elluch,

Bejar, & Technology, 1999). In industrial processes, the use of thermostable amylases has several benefits, including reduced danger of contamination, the expense of external cooling, improved substrate solubility, and lower viscosity allowing for quicker mixing and pumping (Lin, Chyau, Hsu, & biochemistry, 1998). Amylase has emerged as a key enzyme due to its starch hydrolysis activity and the actions that can be carried out because of hydrolysis. One such action is making glucose and fructose syrup from starch (Gupta et al., 2003b). Thermostable amylases are preferred because they save significant energy and lower contamination chances and reaction time. Furthermore, when hydrolysis is performed at higher temperatures, D-glucoses' tendency to polymerize into iso-maltose is reduced (Anto, Trivedi, Patel, & Biotechnology, 2006). β -amylase has a variety of uses both in academic research and in the workplace. It can be

applied to structural research on molecules of starch and glycogen made in a variety of ways and in addition to this, it is employed to create high-maltose syrups (S. Sivaramakrishnan, D. Gangadharan, K. M. Nampoothiri, C. R. Soccol, & A. J. F. T. B. Pandey, 2006). Amylases are produced by some halophilic bacteria that are stable at high salinities and could be used in various difficult industrial processes that use concentrated salt solutions (ARBA, 2015). At high temperatures, (100-110°C), the production of valuable products like glucose, dextrose, dextrose syrup, Maltose, and maltodextrin depends upon the enzymatic liquefaction and saccharification (Asgher, 2007), (Gomes, 2003), (Stamford, 2001). Fungi, mostly *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* are found as terrestrial isolates (Kathiresan, 2006). Industrial enzymes like amylase and food like soy sauce, organic acid, and acetic acid are made primarily using *Aspergillus oryzae* (Kammoun, 2008). Due to its acidity tolerance ($\text{pH} \leq 3$), *Aspergillus niger* has significant hydrolytic abilities in the synthesis of amylase and permits the avoidance of bacterial contamination (Teixeira-Costa, 2022). *Thermomyces lanuginosus*, a thermophilic fungus, excels in producing amylase (Jensen, 2002) (Kunamneni, 2005).

2.5.1. Molecular Applications:

To study the gene expression and elements of regulatory genes, regulatory gene assay is very

important (AUBEL et al., 2001). In addition to antibiotic resistance the presence of amylase is an alternative technique for selecting the reporter constructer effective integration in molecular biology. To determine amylolytic activity loss, the iodine staining method is cost-effective and convenient (Ikuta et al., 1990).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Description of the study area:

Soil samples were collected from six different locations in the Abbottabad District: the Salhad damping site, Salhad fields, Havelian fruit mandi damping site, garden soil of Ayub Medical complex, Nathiagali, and Poultry farm Kakul village Abbottabad. Abbottabad is situated in the Hazara region of Eastern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Salhad is a subdivision of Abbottabad, located 2 km south of the main city. Havelian is a town, situated 12 km away from Abbottabad. Kakul is a village situated in the district Abbottabad, at an elevation of thirteen hundred meters, northeast of the entrance of Abbottabad city. Nathiagali is a hill station and mountain resort town located in the district of Abbottabad. Abbottabad itself positioned about 120 km north of Islamabad and 150 km east of Peshawar. It has an altitude of 1,256m above sea level and the annual rainfall in Abbottabad is 1532 mm. A detailed description is shown in the figure below

Figure 6: Description of the study area

3.2. Sample collection:

A total of 12 samples were collected, with 2 samples taken from each specificity mentioned earlier. The soil samples were carefully obtained from a depth of 12cm beneath the earth's surface using an aseptic spatula and placed in sterile plastic bags. Each sample was labeled with the site of collection and date. Subsequently, the samples were transferred to the laboratory and stored for processing.

Figure 8: LB agar media

3.4. Isolation of bacteria

To isolate the bacteria from the soil sample the method of serial dilution was employed. For serial dilution, initially, 1g of soil sample was dissolved in 9 ml of distilled water, and subsequent dilutions were made up to 10^7 of each sample. Following the serial dilution 0.1ml of diluted sample from each dilution was carefully pipetted on LB agar media that contain peptone 10g, NaCl 5g, yeast extract 5g, and agar 17g per 1000ml of distilled water, and the diluted sample was evenly spread onto a separate plate using a sterile

3.3. Media Preparation:

Media used in this experiment is Luria-Bertani (LB) agar composed of 10g of peptone, 5g NaCl, 5g of yeast extract, and 17g of agar per 1000 ml of distilled water. Additionally, LB broth that contains 10g of peptone, 5g of NaCl, and 5g of yeast extract per 1000ml of water and starch agar media is formulated with 10g of starch, 10g of peptone, 5g of NaCl, 5g of yeast extract and 17g of agar per 1000ml of distilled water.

Figure 9: LB broth media

spreader. The plates were subsequently incubated at a temperature of 32°C for a duration of 24 hr. After precisely 24hr of incubation, distinctive types of colonies appeared on the plates. Each colony was streaked on LB agar media plates by using a sterile wire loop. Following additional 24hrs incubation at 32°C pure cultures were successfully obtained. Preserved the pure culture for further process.

3.5. Designation of Isolates:

The bacterial isolates have been systematically labeled using the alphabet 'A' followed by sequential

numbering. Accordingly, the isolates collected from the soil samples of the Salhad damping site, Salhad fields, and Havelian fruit mandi damping site, garden soil of Ayub Medical complex, Nathiagali, and Poultry farm Kakul village Abbottabad were designated as A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6, A7, A8, A9, A10, A11, A12, A13, A14, A15.

3.6. Morphological identification:

For morphological identification of suspected isolates, we used the Gram staining method and also performed the motility test of these isolates.

3.6.1. Gram staining

To determine whether the isolates are positive or negative gram staining technique is used. We performed Gram staining of isolates. First labeled microscopic slides with the name of isolates added one drop of distilled water on the slide. Next, the isolates were picked from the pure culture with the help of a sterile wire loop and transferred it to the slide. Prepared a thin smear of culture on a glass slide heat-fixed by using a flame. A few drops of crystal violet were added to the smear and washed with tap water after 1 minute. Next solution of gram iodine was added and retained for 1 minute. Iodine reacts with crystal violet to form a di-iodine complex to decrease solubility in the cells. After 1 minute rinsed it with water and decolorized it with 95% Ethyl alcohol commonly called decolourizer for 30 seconds. Washed it with water. At this stage, the gram-positive cells appeared purple while the gram-negative appeared colorless. Countered stain by adding safranin stain. After 1 minute washed the stain and dry the slide. Oil immersion was added and examined the slides under the microscope at 100x.

3.6.2. Motility test

A motility test is very important to determine the behavior of bacteria and their ability to move. To check the motility of isolates, semisolid LB agar media was prepared that contained 10g of peptone, 5g of NaCl, 5g of yeast extract, and 17g of agar per 1000 ml of distilled water. Each Bacterial isolates were stab cultured in separate tubes with the help of a straight wire loop. Incubated for 24-48hr at 32°C, after 24-48hrs the movements of isolates were observed in test tubes.

3.6.3. Colonies morphology:

Colony morphology refers to observable change characteristics of a group of microorganisms growing on a solid culture medium. Colonies' morphology was determined by examining their size, shape, color, optical properties, texture, margin, and opacity of colony. In this study, bacteria were streaked on nutrient media and observed colony morphology.

3.7. Biochemical testing

3.7.2.1. Coagulase test

This test was used to distinguish between bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* that produce coagulase enzymes and bacteria which do not produce coagulase enzymes like *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. This test was performed on a glass slide. A single drop of serum was added to a slide. Subsequently, a bacterial colony was picked using a sterile loop or glass rod. Observations were made for clump formation or agglutination.

3.7.2.2. Catalase test

This test was used to differentiate bacteria that produce catalase from non-catalase-producing bacteria. Hydrogen peroxide was used as a reagent. 1-2 drops of hydrogen peroxide were carefully added to the slide. The colony was taken from 24 hours of incubated culture by using a sterile wire loop or a glass rod. When the colony was introduced into hydrogen peroxide solution, immediately observed the formation of bubbles.

3.7.2.3. Oxidase test

This test was performed on filter paper utilizing Kovac's reagent oxidase reagent. To prepare the oxidase reagent 0.01g Kovac's reagent was dissolved in 9 ml distilled water. Subsequently, 2-3 drops of oxidase reagent were added on filter paper and picked a well-isolated colony using a sterile loop. The chosen colony was gently smeared on filter paper. The phenylenediamine present in the reagent underwent oxidation leading to a deep purple color. The color change was observed in 5-10 seconds. The dark purple color of the colony showed positive results. If there were no color changes, the results would be negative.

3.7.2.4. Indole test

This test was used to assess the ability of bacteria to hydrolyze tryptophan and produce indole. The test was performed using test tubes. After 48 hours of incubation of the culture broth, it was transferred into a test tube. Subsequently, a commercially prepared Kovac's reagent that contains para-dimethylamino Benz aldehyde was added to the test tube. 5 drops of Kovac's reagent were added to a test tube. The red-colored ring was formed on the upper layer of the tube which indicates the presence of indole. While the yellow-color ring showed negative results.

3.7.2.5. Methyl-red test

This test was used to check the ability of organisms to produce a significant quantity of stable acids. For this test, a methyl red reagent was prepared. 0.025g of methyl red was added to 20 ml of a 95% ethanol solution. Following this, the addition of distilled water resulted in a 50ml solution of the reagent. This reagent was introduced into 48 hours of culture broth. The color changed from yellow to red, which was observed due to the production of acid.

3.8. Primary screening of amylase-producing bacteria

For screening of amylase-producing bacteria starch hydrolysis test was conducted. For the starch hydrolysis test, starch agar media were prepared that contained 10g of starch, 10g of peptone, 5g of NaCl, and 5g of yeast extract per 1000 ml of distilled water. The media were poured into plates and allowed to solidify. Bacterial isolates were then inoculated on the plate using the dot method with the help of a toothpick and incubated at 32°C for 24-48 hours in an inverted position. After incubation, plates were flooded with iodine solution with the help of a dropper for a few seconds. A zone of hydrolysis was observed around the grown colonies and observations were recorded. To calculate the ratio between the diameter of the clear zone surrounding the colonies and the diameter of the colonies the following formula was used:

$$\frac{\text{Solubility index (SI)}}{\text{Diameter of halo zone + diameter of colony (mm)}} = \frac{\text{Diameter of colony (mm)}}{\text{Diameter of colony (mm)}}$$

Equation 3.1 Solubility Index

3.8.2. Secondary screening of amylase-producing bacteria

The potential isolates were subsequently assessed for their ability to produce enzymes. The isolates that were producing the maximum quantity of amylase were chosen for further process.

3.8.2.1. Submerged Fermentation:

For submerged fermentation, the standard inoculum was prepared. To prepare the inoculum three isolates were selected that show the maximum zone of hydrolysis in starch test. Isolates were cultured in 20ml of inoculum media that contain 10g of starch, 10g of peptone, 1g of KH₂PO₄, 0.01g of MgCl₂, and 5g of yeast extract per 1000ml of distilled water. Cultures were then incubated at 37°C for 48-72 hours of incubation, the culture had a viable count of cells. The cultures with the viable count of 2-3×10⁶ cells/ml served as the inoculum for the production medium. The production medium composition was similar to the inoculum medium. For the fermentation process, 5% of each inoculum medium was inoculated in 50ml of sterile production medium, in 250ml Erlenmeyer flask separately incubated the flask at 37°C on rotatory shaker at 150rpm for 48hrs. Microorganisms utilized the nutrient present in production medium resulting in the production of the product.

3.8.2.2. Separation of Crude enzyme from culture media:

After incubation, the cultures fluid obtained were centrifuged at 7000rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. The centrifugation resulted in the formation of two layers. The pellet, which contained bacteria, was discarded while the supernatant was the crude enzyme. This crude enzyme was utilized to check the enzyme activity.

3.8.2.3. Crude Enzyme Activity:

To assess the enzymatic activity starch agar media was prepared that contain 10g of peptone, 5g of NaCl, 5g of yeast extract, 17 g of agar, and 10g of starch per 1000ml of distilled water. Sterilized media was poured into sterile petri plates and allowed to solidify. On solidifying wells were then created in the centre of plates using a sterile cork borer. Poured each supernatant into wells by using a micropipette. Plates

were incubated for a duration of 24hr at a temperature of 32°C. After 24hrs incubation plates were flooded with iodine solution and clear zones developed around the wells were observed as an indicator of enzyme activity.

Soil was a source from which the bacterias isolated. Soil mixed of different types of decays was serial diluted. After serial dilution, random dilution were picked and spread on the LB agar media plates that are shown in figure From sample 15 isolates were streak on LB media that are shown in figure below:

4. RESULTS

4.1 Isolation of bacteria:

Figure 10: Spreading plates

A1

A2

A3

A4

A5

A6

A10

A11

A12

A13

A14

A15

Figure 11: streaking plates

4.2 Morphological characterization of amylase producing bacteria

4.2.1 Colonies morphology:

The colonies morphology was examined by observing freshly streaked culture on nutrient agar media and LB media that is illustrated in a table below:

Table 4.1: Morphological identification

Stain ID	Color	Optical Properties	Texture	Margin/Edges	Spreading	Shape
A1	Creamy	Opaque	Dry and smooth	Irregular	Positive	Irregular
A2	Creamy	Opaque	Dry and smooth	Irregular	Positive	Irregular
A3	Yellow	Opaque	Smooth and shiny	Undulating	Negative	Puncti form
A4	White	Opaque	Smooth and dry	Irregular	Positive	Irregular
A5	Colorless	Transparent	Moist and shine	Undulating	Positive	Spindle
A6	Colorless	Transparent	Smooth and shiny	Irregular	Positive	Irregular
A7	Grey	Opaque	Dry and smooth	Irregular	Positive	Spindle
A8	Colorless	Opaque	Smooth and shiny	Entire	Negative	Spindle
A9	Colorless	Transparent	Dry and rough	Entire	Negative	Puncti form
A10	Grey	Opaque	Dry and smooth	Entire	Positive	Spindle
A11	White	Opaque	Dry and smooth	Entire	Negative	Puncti form
A12	Grey	Opaque	Dry and smooth	Entire	Positive	Spindle
A13	Colorless	Transparent	Rough and shiny	Irregular	Negative	Irregular
A14	White	Opaque	Dry and smooth	Entire	Negative	Puncti form
A15	Creamy	Opaque	Dry and smooth	Entire	Positive	Spindle

Figure.12: Morphological identification on nutrient media

Gram staining:

Among 15 bacterial strains 7 strains are gram positive while 8 strains were gram negative, predominantly rods only, with only few bacteria appearing as cocci and arranged in clusters and chains. Moreover, few of them were found in individual form when examined under microscope

after Gram staining. This shown in table and figures below:

4.2.2 Motility Test:

During motility test most strains showed no motility indicating limited movement. However, a small subset of bacterial strains exhibited motility.

Table 4.2 Gram staining

Stain ID	Color	Shape	Arrangement	Size	G+/G-	Motility
A1	Pink	Cocci	Clustered	Small	G-	-
A2	Pink	Rod	Individual	Small	G-	+
A3	Purple	Rod	Individual	Medium	G+	-
A4	Pink	Rod	Chain	Medium	G-	+
A5	Purple	Rod	Individual	Medium	G+	-
A6	Pink	Rod	Pair	Small	G-	+
A7	Pink	Rod	Clustered	Large	G-	-
A8	Pink	Cocci	Clustered	Small	G-	-
A9	Purple	Cocci	Clustered	Large	G+	-
A10	Purple	Rods	Chain	Large	G+	-
A11	Purple	Rod	Chain	Long	G+	-
A12	Pink	Rod	Clustered	Small	G-	-
Stain ID	Color	Shape	Arrangement	Size	G+/G-	Motility
A13	Purple	Rod	Individual	Long	G+	-
A14	Pink	Rod	Cluster	Small	G-	-
A15	Purple	Rod	Chain	Long	G+	-

Figure 13: Gram staining

4.3 Biochemical characterization

Among the 15 bacterial isolates, 11 have tested positive for the oxidase test, indicating the presence of specific enzymes. Additionally, all of the isolates demonstrated the capability to produce catalase enzymes, thus classifying them as nitrogen fixing bacteria. Furthermore, the majority of these strains have yielded positive results in the coagulase test,

suggesting their potential to form clots. only 1 bacterial strains have shown a negative response in the methyl red test, indicating distinct metabolic characteristics. In contrast, during the indole test, the majority of the stains exhibited positive results, signifying the production of indole. Results are presented in the table positives are shown with + and negatives are represented with -.

Table 4.3: Results of Biochemical tests

Strains ID	Catalase	Oxidase	Coagulase	Methyl-red	Indole Production
A1	+	-	-	+	+
A2	+	+	-	+	+
A3	+	+	+	+	+
A4	+	+	+	+	+
A5	+	+	+	+	+
Strains ID	Catalase	Oxidase	Coagulase	Methyl-red	Indole Production
A6	+	+	+	+	+
A7	+	+	+	-	+
A8	+	-	+	+	-
A9	+	-	+	+	+
A10	+	+	-	+	-
A11	+	+	+	+	+
A12	+	+	+	+	-

A13	+	+	+	+	+
A14	+	-	+	+	+
A15	+	+	+	+	+

Figure 14: Results of Oxidase test

Figure 15: Results of the catalase test

Figure 16: Results of Methyl-red test

Figure 17: Results of Indole production test

4.4 Primary screening of amylase producing bacteria

The gram iodine method was used to observe the presence of clear zones around the colonies in the starch hydrolysis test of bacterial isolates. Out of 15 bacterial isolates tested, 12 of them exhibited clear zones around their colonies, indicating amylase activity. However, one isolate showed no growth at all, and the other two isolates grew but did not display a clear zone around them, suggesting the absence of amylase activity. Among 15 bacterial

isolates, approximately 84% (12 out of 15) demonstrated positive results with clear zones, indicating their ability to hydrolyze starch. Conversely, 13% (2 out 15) of isolates did not show any hydrolysis zone, implying that these isolates did not exhibit any growth at all. Among the isolates that showed positive amylase activity (80% of total isolates) approximately 33% of them displayed high amylolytic activity, surpassing the amylase production level of their isolates, which exhibited only moderate activity.

Figure 18: Percentage of Amylase and non-amylase-producing bacteria

Figure 19: Comparison of clear zones of strains in primary screening

Table 4.3: Solubility Index

Stain ID	Colony diameter	Zone diameter	Solubility index
A1	2.8cm	3.7cm	2.32cm
A2	3cm	4cm	2.33cm
A3	1.7cm	3cm	2.7cm
A4	2cm	2.7cm	2.35cm

A5	–	–	–
A6	3.9cm	4.4cm	2.13cm
A7	1.4cm	2.8cm	3cm
A8	0.7cm	2.4cm	4.4cm
A9	–	–	–
A10	1.5cm	3.2cm	3.1cm
A11	1.4cm	2.9cm	3.07cm
A12	2.1cm	3cm	2.4cm
A13	–	–	–
A14	1.3cm	2cm	2.5cm
Stain ID	Colony diameter	Zone diameter	Solubility index
A15	1.5cm	2.8cm	2.8cm

Figure 20: Clear zone Gram iodine method

4.5 Evaluation of enzymes production in submerged fermentation and Enzyme activity assessment:

Following the primary screening of amylase-producing bacteria, three isolates (A1, A2, A3) that exhibited maximum clear zones repeatedly in the starch hydrolysis test were selected for further evaluation of enzyme production. Submerged

fermentation was employed to assess their ability to produce amylase in a production medium. The crude enzyme was extracted from the three selected isolates and their activities were evaluated using the well-diffusion method. Each isolate's crude enzyme was introduced into wells created in a starch agar plate, and the plate was incubated for 24hrs. Subsequently, the plate was flooded with iodine solution to

visualize the hydrolysis zones surrounding the wells. All three isolates (A1, A2, A3) demonstrated considerable amylolytic activity, as evidenced by the prominent clear zone around the wells. Among them, isolate A2 exhibited particularly high amylolytic

activity, displaying the largest hydrolysis zone, indicating its superior potential for amylase production. Crude enzyme activity is shown in the figures below:

Figure 21: Comparison of clear zones in the secondary screening of Amylase-producing-bacteria

Table 4.4: Solubility index in secondary screening

Stain ID	Zone diameter	Diameter of well	Solubility index
A1	2cm	0.8cm	1.5cm
A2	2.5cm	0.8cm	4.125cm
A3	1.8cm	0.8cm	3.25cm

Figure 22: Clear zones around wells by Gram iodine method

The finding of this study signifies the significance of these amylase-producing bacterial isolates, particularly A2, for potential industrial applications. Their robust enzymatic activity indicates their potential as valuable sources for the large-scale production of amylase. Further investigation into the optimization of enzyme production and the underlying genetic mechanisms of isolates A2 are warranted to unlock its full biotechnological potential. These results may pave the way for cost-effective and eco-friendly enzyme production strategies, offering practical alternatives to conventional commercial sources.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

Enzymes are important for carrying biochemical processes within living organisms as well as also plays very crucial role in industrial sector for production of huge amount of products due to the their high specificity and catalytic activity. Amylase is a one those enzyme that play important role in industrial sector. Amylase is frequently use through out the world in food, textile, paper, detergent pharmaceutical as well as chemical industries on routine basis (El-Fallal et al., 2012).

Presently, microbes play important role in the production enzymes that are cost-effective. Many industries rely on microbial enzyme because it is essential catalyst to convert the raw material into end product. Therefore, screening of high amylase producing microorganisms are very essential in indentification of different amylases that are suitable for industrial production (Demirkan, Sevgi, & Başkurt, 2017).

Different reports are on isolation of amylase producing bacteria from the soil samples in various geographical areas. However, to the best of my knowledge no such investigation has been conducted from these sites of the district Abbottabad. In our research, we focused on collecting soil samples from specific locations: the Salhad damping site, Salhad fields and Havelian fruit mandi damping site, garden soil of Ayub Medical complex, Nathiagali, and Poultry farm Kakul village Abbottabad. Our main goal was to discover the bacteria that produce amylase in these areas. This will aid existing knowledge and may have practical uses in industries.

This study focused on the isolation and characterization of amylase-producing bacteria from specific locations in district Abbottabad. Among the 15 bacterial isolates, 12 exhibited positive amylase activity, indicating their potential for industrial application. Out of these, isolates A2 showed particularly high amyolytic activity, making it a promising candidate for large-scale amylase production. The finding suggests that these bacterial isolates, especially A2, hold significant biotechnological potential for cost-effective and eco-friendly enzyme production in various industries. To fully utilize their enzymatic capabilities further investigation into the optimization of the enzyme production and the genetic mechanisms of isolate A2 are recommended. These efforts may pave the way for practical alternatives to conventional commercial sources, advancing industrial processes and contributing to our understanding of enzymatic activities in microbial systems.

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